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**IMPLEMENTATION OF CCE & USE OF MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING AND
LEARNING**

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Abstract:

As the Right of Children to Free And Compulsory Education Act 2009 was enforced; Govt. implemented Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) system in Maharashtra from August 2010 . CCE has recommended Formative & Summative Evaluation. Formative Evaluation continues throughout the year whereas Summative Evaluation includes Term-end Exams. CCE has suggested eight tools of Formative Evaluation. They are Daily Observations, Oral Work, Practical's /Experiments, Activities, Projects, Tests, Assignment/Class work and Any other tool. To cope up with the new method of evaluation; methods of teaching & strategies of learning need to be modified. Teachers are expected to take care of "values, core elements of the syllabus and life skills" during the teaching learning process. Many training programmes have been organised for them, yet they find difficulty in the implementation of CCE. The present paper discusses how and which modern methods of teaching and learning can be used to suit the system of CCE.

Introduction:

Vinoba Bhave described Education as that which cannot be taught. Many educationists also emphasized that child has the capacity to learn on his own. Teachers' job is to facilitate him in learning. Hence we can say that we must not try to teach, instead we must try to make students learn. Teaching, Learning & Evaluation are inseparable parts of Educational Process. All the educational activities are planned keeping in mind the method of Evaluation. After the enforcement of Right to Education (RTE), the method of Evaluation in schools has been totally

changed as Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE). Hence methods of teaching & strategies of learning need to be modified.

Introduction of CCE:

Our evaluation/ exam. Systems were criticized since years. National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986 recommended the need to adopt CCE. Though some changes were brought in the curricula framed in 1988 but CCE was not implemented. After NPE's recommendations; Dr. R.H.Dave Committee was formed to decide the Minimum Level of Learning (MLL) to be achieved at the end of each class. Its report also stressed the importance of CCE. It says----- "A sound evaluation programme, if carefully designed & effectively implemented as an integral part of an overall educational programme ,can be of immense value in maintaining & enhancing the Quality of learning. On the other hand, if learner's evaluation is neglected or if a scheme of evaluation is rigid, ritualistic and lopsided; it can prove equally harmful and damaging to the very objective of ensuring the quality of education. Under the MLL programme, therefore, it is one of the essential pre- conditions that a comprehensive, illuminative and improvement-oriented evaluation plan is properly developed and consistently practiced."

National Curriculum Framework (NCF) 2005 also recommended the need for new evaluation system. It recommended that -----"There should be more varied modes of assessment beyond the examination hall paper-pencil test. Oral testing and group work evaluation should be encouraged. Open-book exam. and exams without time limits are worth introducing. These innovations would have the added advantage of shifting the focus of exams from testing memory to testing higher level competencies such as interpretation, analysis and problem solving skills."

The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act was enforced in 2009 and Govt. of Maharashtra made Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) system compulsory from August 2010.

Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) system:

According to CCE students are to be evaluated continuously during their learning process. How the child learns? What good qualities he has? Where he finds difficulty? All these questions are answerable through CCE. Instead of giving due importance to memory; CCE

emphasizes on the development of students' Understanding, Application, Thinking and Creativity. Along with their Intellectual development, their Physical & Emotional aspects are also kept in mind in CCE. It is expected that students should not only learn to read and write properly, they should also speak nicely, play well, observe their environment and learn on their own. They should learn practically and their personality should shine in an All Round Way.

CCE has recommended Formative & Summative Evaluation. Formative Evaluation continues throughout the year and Summative Evaluation includes Term-end Exams. CCE has suggested eight tools of Formative Evaluation. They are---- 'Daily Observations, Oral Work, Practicals/Experiments, Activities, Projects, Tests, Assignment/Class work and Any other tool'.

Implementation of CCE:

CCE is completing two years in primary schools (up to Std. VIII) of Maharashtra. Teachers have attended many training programmes for its proper utilization. In an informal talk with the school teachers it was found that teachers face a lot of problems in its implementation as they are still not clear about the use of various tools suggested for Formative Assessment. Hence still the need is there for guidance to teachers. They need to be Creative in their Teaching Learning process. They need to use various modern methods and strategies of Teaching & Learning to implement these tools properly.

Modern methods/ strategies/techniques of teaching and learning which can be used to cope up with CCE:

Teachers are expected to take care of ten basic values, core elements and life skills while teaching in the class. They have to use various tools of Formative Assessment. For all these they have to be very creative in their approach. Few methods/ strategies/techniques of teaching and learning are discussed here to suit the Evaluation techniques.

- **Co-operative Learning:** It is a learning process in which the students get opportunities to learn by themselves in a group in a co-operative environment by forming a number of teams, each team consisting of a small number of students of different levels of ability for the understanding of the subject. They share all information among themselves and help each other for having the required knowledge,

understanding and application of one or the other aspects of the content material or course units included in their syllabus.

- Using this technique we can pay attention to many values, core elements of syllabus and life skills. We can also use tools of evaluation like observation and group activity.
- **Brain Storming Strategy:** It implies to storming of brain i.e. to evolve or generate a number of ideas as quickly as possible. This strategy can be used with a group to explore a number of ideas related to a situation or solution of a problem without passing any judgment. This strategy is specially useful for the development of higher cognitive abilities like reflective thinking, creative imagination and problem solving. To start with, a small group of students is formed. They are provided with a focus, e.g. “student unrest” and asked to think about the solution of the problem and give their ideas one by one as rapidly as possible. They are advised to storm the problem with all possible ideas and solutions. At the end of the Brain Storming session, all the solutions and ideas received from the members are discussed in a free and frank democratic environment. Out of this discussion the most viable ideas are aCCEpted for the solution of the problem in hand.
- Using this technique also we can pay attention to many values, core elements of syllabus and life skills. We can also use tools of evaluation like observation and group activity.
- **Project strategy :** This strategy tries to impart education of all the subjects in an integrated way by correlating them with the real life activities. The selection of a topic for a project depends on a teacher and the subject she teaches. For example a Science teacher can opt for the project of establishment of a science museum, neighbouring birds and insects, electrification of the school campus etc. a History teacher can have the project of collection of coins. This strategy is child-centered, provides freedom of working in a social environment and it provides integration of physical and mental activities.it developes positive attitude towards manual work and provides teaching through correlation.
- **Role-play :** It is a teaching strategy in which a situation is dramatised by a group by playing specific roles, as desired by the situation, under the direction of of a

teacher for deriving useful educational experiences. For example, for acquainting students with the problems and ill effects of over affection, and protection given to a male child by his parents, the situation may be enacted by the students by playing the roles of parents, brothers and sisters, child and other family members and companions. This technique provides spontaneous, unrehearsed life-like presentation of some situation for gaining insight into a specific problem or deriving useful educative experiences.

- This technique can help the teacher to prepare students for various life skills.
- **Computer Assisted Instructions:** The instructional work carried out with the help of computers is called Computer Assisted Instructions (CAI). It provides a purposeful interaction between a learner and the computer device for helping the individual learner achieve the desired instructional objectives with his own pace and abilities at his command. CAI helps the teacher to bring the entire world in the classroom, to make abstract concepts concrete.
- **Group Discussion Strategy:** It is the interchange of ideas between students and the teacher or among a group of students, resulting into active learning for the realization of the predetermined teaching learning objectives. This technique trains the students for carrying out group activities and cooperative tasks. Proper social development and democratic living is also developed with the adoption of this strategy.
- **Dramatization Strategy:** It is the teaching strategy, helpful in understanding the concepts and events related to various subjects of the school curriculum by converting them into an act of play or drama. The events of the past, the unreachable present and the abstract concepts, quite difficult in comprehension, become too lively, interesting and comprehending on the part of the students with this single act of dramatization. Dramatization develops the language and communication skills specially for teaching the second and third languages it proves to be the best method.

- **Some more strategies:** Apart from the above mentioned methods and strategies a teacher can use the methods like ---Independent Study Strategy, Supervised Study and Constructivist Approach and meet the challenges faced by today's teacher.

Some Suggestions:

CCE has provided an opportunity to the teachers to be innovative in their approach. They should welcome CCE and try to use various innovative methods of teaching

